

LEADERSHIP AND PERSONAL PLAN

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Abstract: Leadership is a system of interactions in a team in which one person (the leader) takes the initiative and undertakes responsibility for actions and their potential repercussions. Some theoretical assumptions regarding leadership conduct exist. The framework of the educational process, as well as the social purposes of teaching and educational activities, are defined by leadership. The problem of leadership as a social phenomenon has been studied for many hundreds and even thousands of years. Even in ancient China, during the time of Confucius, there was a discussion about what is more important for a leader: power, the art of management or knowledge of the laws. It was believed that if the leader (ruler) does not know the art of management, then he will be misled at the top and he will not be able to identify the treacherous.

Key words: leadership, personal plan, managerial leadership, organizational activity, personal qualities

Introduction

There are many works in scientific literature devoted to the problem of leadership. There are many studies of the place, role and characteristics of managerial leadership. However, mostly in these works, the concepts of leadership are considered in relation to entrepreneurship, business and educational processes. Apparently, the main approaches, tasks, characteristics, models of managerial leadership for all objects of organizational activity have much in common. It is also obvious that leadership problems have their own special features in the educational process. Leadership, as a specific type of managerial relationship, although management and leadership are not synonymous, is a social impact on a group of people to achieve certain goals. In this regard, it is advisable to consider the role of managerial leadership in the field of education in a hierarchical order: in the highest level of management of educational institutions, in departments of universities, universities, as well as in departments and further – in student groups. Let's try to note the approach to leadership, its features, tasks, forms and possibly features of in relation to an important link of management in educational institutions - educational departments. Managerial leadership is the interaction between the members of the team, in the center of which is the leader on whose personal qualities the successful and effective activities of this unit, its effectiveness and social significance largely depend.

Materials and Methods

Leadership is a two-way process that involves interaction between the leader and team members. The managerial activity of the leader involves the formulation and solution of a wide range of problems. This is, first of all, the definition of the goals and objectives of the department, including each member of the team. This is the formation of the department and control over its structure. An important task of the leader is to manage the department and monitor the implementation of its tasks by its members. The leader should carry out official

and unofficial contacts not only within the group, but also the outside world. For the successful functioning of the educational institution, the leader must provide the necessary conditions for each of its members. For the successful fulfillment of the tasks set in the field of activity of a managerial leader, control over the socio-psychological atmosphere at the department and the development of interpersonal relations plays an important role. Psychology distinguishes two types of leadership: formal and informal. Formal leadership is usually identified with the activities of the head, as a representative of legitimate authority. So thus, the head of the department is a formal leader. Such leadership is based on legal relations. At the same time, the effectiveness of the functioning of the department as a group activity depends on the degree of activity of its members, coordination in achieving the tasks set and is impossible without formal leadership. The characteristics of the team members play an important role in the choice of leadership styles. If the latter are passive, do not show interest in the results of the group's work, the leader is forced to apply an authoritarian leadership style. In addition, the researchers note, in cases of lack or unavailability of information, team members are deprived of the opportunity to use it, and, therefore, cannot make appropriate decisions. It also entails an authoritarian management style. In the corporate world, collegial leadership style is becoming increasingly important when the leader engages the team or its individual members in discussion and decision-making, depending on their skill level. It seems that in the work of academic departments of universities, a democratic leadership style combined with a collegial one is preferred. However, under certain circumstances, the leader has the right to apply an authoritarian management style. With a functional approach to managerial leadership, some researchers distinguish three interrelated areas of activity: the fulfillment of tasks; the creation of collective; personal development.

Results

Informal leadership is informal in nature and goes beyond the scope of the position, although the leader can be an informal leader at the same time. Leadership is characterized by something more than a formal position. The leader must have special personal characteristics, pronounced features. In many literary sources devoted to the art of management, personal traits of leadership are formulated. At the same time, the nature of leadership may differ at the macro and micro levels. Macro-leadership is focused on the external environment, on the future. The micro-leader functions in the internal environment of the organization and solves current problems. The head of the department is a leader at the micro level with elements of macro leadership. He must have such personal qualities as intellectual abilities, behavioral competence, self-confidence, activity, entrepreneurship, sociability. However, having these qualities does not necessarily lead to leadership. It is important that the leader's personality corresponds to the tasks and goals facing the educational institution, the direction of its activities, as well as the relationship with the team. If the team leader does not fully meet these conditions, is not able to effectively interact with the surrounding members of the team, informal leadership spontaneously arises. Informal leadership is based on informal relationships and can arise within a separate group that is in opposition or antipathy to the collective as a whole. Informal leadership is not stable and is conditioned by the personal authority of such a leader in a particular group. Such leadership presupposes a twofold outcome. This is the adoption of appropriate sanctions by the formal leader. Or there may be a need for a higher-level management leader to determine the compliance of the formal leader

of this unit the current requirements of the management process in an educational institution. The fulfillment of the task assigned to the team is the main and primary responsibility of the leader. This is the successful implementation of educational, methodological, research, educational work by members of the team. The creation of the organizational structure of the team, the effective interaction of its members contributes to the fulfillment of the tasks set. The leader must ensure that the team members interact in such a way that they focus their activities, first of all, on achieving common ideas and objectives.

Discussions

Researchers of managerial leadership distinguish several leadership styles: authoritarian (autocratic), democratic, liberal (self-detached). An authoritarian leader seeks to concentrate all power in his hands, dictates rules and procedures, and is subjective in his assessments. A democratic leader delegates authority to employees, promotes their participation in the development of the main directions of the management process, is objective in assessments. The liberal leader specifically withdraws himself from participation in the affairs of the collective, giving him complete freedom of action when performing certain tasks. Studies have shown that with an autocratic leadership style, teams work well only in the presence of a leader. However, the rigid autocratic leadership style is perceived negatively by employees, an atmosphere of hostility arises. With authoritarian leadership, mistakes made by the team are blamed on some members of the group, i.e. there is obvious criticism and subjectivity in assessments. With a democratic leadership style, the effectiveness of the group's activities is no less high than with an authoritarian style, but the relationships in the team are very positive. Team members make equally intense efforts, both in the presence and in the absence of the leader. When the authoritarian leader was replaced by a liberal one, the hostility and aggressiveness of the group members who had been restrained earlier increased. As a result, the effectiveness of the team's activities decreased.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that a managerial leader should strive for a balance in his management teams between personal development, the creation of a well-coordinated team and the fulfillment of tasks. If a leader is team-oriented and considers himself a member of this team, then his leadership decisions are unlikely to satisfy all members of the team. The predominant attention to the process of collectivism will lead to a deterioration in the development and moral state of individuals. Finally, when focusing on the development of personalities, more attention may be paid by one employee to the detriment of others. On the one hand, this may be due to the presence of more trained, capable workers who receive complex tasks. In other cases, the leader takes care of insufficiently professionally trained employees.

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